

Machine Learning Code Understanding

Investigating Machine Learning Code Understanding.

You will be asked to give your consent to participate in the research and will answer a set of questions involving: a brief characterization; questions about code comprehension; and a brief finalization.

The questionnaire takes around 20 minutes and your contribution will help us in the scientific advancement of software engineering for machine learning.

To thank you for your contribution, we will raffle 5 physical books on Software Engineering for Data Science among the survey respondents. Thank you for your cooperation!

1. E-mail *

Consent Form

This study aims to understand the impact of design principles on understanding machine learning code.

The research follows a high academic standard and is conducted anonymously. We will not associate your name or email address with your responses. In addition, you may request that your information be removed from this study at any time.

2. Name: *

3.

*

I declare my consent to participate in the research:

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes.

No.

Participants' characterization

4. 1) Highest level of education : *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

None.

Bachelor's Degree.

Post-Graduate Specialization.

Master's Degree.

Doctoral Degree.

5. 2) Do you have any academic degree related to computer science? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes.

No.

6. 2.1) If yes, what ?

7. 3) What is your experience with software development? (More than one option can be selected) *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- I have never developed software.
- I have been developing for my own use.
- I have been developing as team member, related to a course.
- I have been developing as team member, in industry.

8. 3.1) What is your experience with software development in years? *

9. 4) What is your experience with Machine Learning (ML) software development? (More than one option can be selected) *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- I never developed ML software.
- I developed ML software for my own use.
- I developed ML software as a team member, related to a course.
- I developed ML software as a team member in the industry.

10. 4.1) What is your experience with Machine Learning software development in years? *

11. 5) Please, select for each topic the level of your experience following the 5 points scale (look at the subtitle):

*

Subtitle:

1 = No experience.

2 = I studied in a classroom or in a book.

3 = I actively practiced in a classroom project.

4 = I used it in one project in industry.

5 = I used it in several projects in industry.

Marcar apenas uma oval por linha.

	1	2	3	4	5
Object-oriented programming	<input type="radio"/>				
Encapsulation.	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of Inheritance, Abstract Classes and Interfaces.	<input type="radio"/>				
Clean Code.	<input type="radio"/>				
SOLID Principles.	<input type="radio"/>				
Design Patterns.	<input type="radio"/>				
Domain-Driven Design (DDD).	<input type="radio"/>				
Python language.	<input type="radio"/>				

12. 6) How do you rate your English reading and comprehension skills? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Basic.

Intermediate.

Advanced.

Questionário.

The Python code below aims to create a linear regression model using the Scikit-learn library to make predictions based on a dataset. The dataset is loaded from Azure ML Workspace and separated into training and test sets. Then, a linear regression model is created using the training data and evaluated with the test data, where the mean squared error (MSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the model are calculated. Finally, the model is used to make predictions and the results are plotted on a graph comparing predicted values with actual values.

Analyze the code:

```
1 import azureml.core
2 from azureml.core import Workspace
3 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
4 from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
5 from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score
6 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
7 from abc import ABC, abstractmethod
8
9
10 class DataLoader(ABC):
11     """Abstract class that contains operations of a Data Loader."""
12
13     @abstractmethod
14     def dataset(self):
15         """Method that returns a dataset."""
16         pass
17
18
19 class DataLoaderFromWorkspace(DataLoader):
20     def __init__(self, workspace, dataset_name):
21         self.__dataset = workspace.datasets.get(dataset_name)
22
23     def dataset(self):
24         return self.__dataset
25
26
```

```

1 class PreProcessor(ABC):
2     """Abstract class that contains operations of a data preprocessor."""
3
4     @abstractmethod
5     def preprocess(self, dataset):
6         """Method that returns the data treated and separated into x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test."""
7         pass
8
9
10 class EspecificPreprocessor(PreProcessor):
11     def __init__(self, seed = 0, test_percentage=0.30):
12         self.__features = ['220NCPFEINF', 'PI 22068AO', '220CARGA/H', 'FC 22046PV', 'FI 22049AO', 'TI 22059AO', 'TC 22010PV']
13         self.__label = 'AM264051BEN'
14         self.__SEED = seed
15         self.__TEST_PERCENTAGE = test_percentage
16
17     def __separate_feature_and_label(self, dataset):
18         dataframe = dataset.to_pandas_dataframe()
19         dataframe.sort_index(inplace=True)
20         x = dataframe[self.__features].values
21         y = dataframe[self.__label].values
22         return x, y
23
24     def preprocess(self, dataset):
25         x, y = self.__separate_feature_and_label(dataset)
26         x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(x, y, test_size=self.__TEST_PERCENTAGE, random_state=self.__SEED)
27         return x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test
28
29

```

```

1 class Model(ABC):
2     """Abstract class that contains operations of a Model."""
3
4     def fit(self, x_train, y_train):
5         """Method to fit the model."""
6         self.model.fit(x_train, y_train)
7
8     def predict(self, x_test):
9         """Method to do predictions."""
10        return self.model.predict(x_test)
11
12
13 class LinearRegressionModel(Model):
14     def __init__(self, is_normalized=True):
15         self.model = LinearRegression(normalize=is_normalized)
16
17

```

```
1 class Evaluator(ABC):
2     """Abstract class that contains operations of an Evaluator."""
3
4     @abstractmethod
5     def evaluate(self,y_test,predictions):
6         """Method that prints the result of the evaluation metrics."""
7         pass
8
9
10 class RegressionEvaluator(Evaluator):
11     """Class that contains operations to evaluate a regression model."""
12
13     def calculate_mean_squared_error(self,y_test,predictions):
14         """Method that returns the mean squared error."""
15         return mean_squared_error(y_test, predictions)
16
17     def calculate_r2_score(self,y_test,predictions):
18         """Method that returns the coefficient of determination R2 Score."""
19         return r2_score(y_test, predictions)
20
21     def evaluate(self,y_test,predictions):
22         print('Mean Squared Error:', self.calculate_mean_squared_error(y_test,predictions))
23         print('R2 score:', self.calculate_r2_score(y_test,predictions))
24
25
```

```
1 class Plotter(ABC):
2     """Abstract class that contains operations of a Plotter."""
3
4     @abstractmethod
5     def plot(self,y_test,predictions):
6         """Method that plots the graph."""
7         pass
8
9
10 class MatPlotter(Plotter):
11     def __init__(self):
12         self.__xlabel = 'Samples'
13         self.__ylabel = 'y and predictions'
14         self.__title = 'y and predictions comparison'
15         self.__legend = 'upper left'
16
17     def plot(self,y_test,predictions):
18         fig = plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4))
19         plt.plot(predictions,"-b", Label="y_hat")
20         plt.plot(self.__y_test,"-r", Label="y")
21         x1,x2,y1,y2 = plt.axis()
22         x1 = 0
23         x2 = 50
24         plt.axis((x1,x2,y1,y2))
25         plt.xlabel(self.__xlabel)
26         plt.ylabel(self.__ylabel)
27         plt.title(self.__title)
28         plt.legend(Loc=self.__legend)
29         plt.show()
30
31
```

```
1 class Controller():
2     """Class that orchestrates a model execution."""
3
4     def __init__(self,dataLoader:DataLoader,preProcessor:PreProcessor,model: Model, evaluator: Evaluator, plotter: Plotter):
5         self.__dataLoader = dataLoader
6         self.__preProcessor = preProcessor
7         self.__model = model
8         self.__evaluator = evaluator
9         self.__plotter = plotter
10
11     def run(self):
12         # Load dataset
13         dataset = self.__dataLoader.dataset()
14         #Preprocessing
15         x_train, x_test, y_train,y_test = self.__preProcessor.preprocess(dataset)
16         #Model Training
17         self.__model.fit(x_train,y_train)
18         #Model Predict
19         predictions = self.__model.predict(x_test)
20         #Evaluation
21         self.__evaluator.evaluate(y_test,predictions)
22         #Plot
23         self.__plotter.plot(y_test,predictions)
24
25
```

```
1 ws = Workspace.from_config()
2 dataset_name = 'revap-u220-pfenc-stream'
3
4 # Create DataLoader
5 dataLoader = DataLoaderFromWorkspace(ws,dataset_name)
6 # Create PreProcessor
7 preProcessor = EspecificPreprocessor()
8 #Create Model
9 model = LinearRegressionModel()
10 #Create Evaluator
11 evaluator = RegressionEvaluator()
12 #Create Plotter
13 plotter = MatPlotter()
14
15 controller = Controller(dataLoader,preProcessor,model,evaluator,plotter)
16 controller.run()
17
18
```

13. 1- What is your perception about understanding the source code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

14. 2- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?

15. 3- The responsibilities in the code above are clearly distributed and defined. *
What is your degree of agreement with the statement?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1- Totally disagree.

2- I disagree.

3- I neither agree nor disagree.

4- I agree.

5- Totally agree.

16. **4- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

17. **5- The code block above has classes structured to have a single responsibility ^{*} in the software, that is, they are specialized in a single subject. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?**

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

18. **6- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

19. **7- The code above is structured so that your classes have a single reason for change. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

20. **8- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

From the analysis of model evaluation metrics, it was observed the need to test other regression algorithms to verify which one can be more effective for the available data set.

We are going to perform software maintenance to allow the use of Ridge Regression, Random Forest Regression and Support Vector Regression algorithms in regression predictions.

The code below adds new Model implementations, through the RidgeRegressionModel, RandomForestRegressorModel and SupportVectorRegressionModel classes and the current controller trains, makes predictions and evaluates the results of all available models.

Analyze the code:

```
1 from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
2 from sklearn.linear_model import Ridge
3 from sklearn.svm import SVR
4
5
6 class RandomForestRegressorModel(Model):
7     def __init__(self, number_of_estimators= 100, SEED = 0):
8         self.model = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=number_of_estimators, random_state=SEED)
9
10
11 class RidgeRegressionModel(Model):
12     def __init__(self, L2_multiplier=1.0):
13         self.model = Ridge(alpha= L2_multiplier)
14
15
16 class SupportVectorRegressionModel(Model):
17     def __init__(self, kernel_type = 'rbf', regularization_parameter = 100):
18         self.model = SVR(kernel=kernel_type, C= regularization_parameter)
19
20
```

```
1 ws = Workspace.from_config()
2 dataset_name = 'revap-u220-pfenc-stream'
3
4 # Create DataLoader
5 dataLoader = DataLoaderFromWorkspace(ws, dataset_name)
6 # Create PreProcessor
7 preProcessor = EspecificPreprocessor()
8 #Create Evaluator
9 evaluator = RegressionEvaluator()
10 #Create Plotter
11 plotter = MatPlotter()
12
13 #Create Models
14 linear_regression_model = LinearRegressionModel()
15 randon_forest_regression_model = RandomForestRegressorModel()
16 ridge_regression_model = RidgeRegressionModel()
17 support_vector_regression_model = SupportVectorRegressionModel()
18
19 #Run Linear Regression
20 Controller(dataLoader, preProcessor, linear_regression_model, evaluator, plotter).run()
21 #Run Random Forest Regression
22 Controller(dataLoader, preProcessor, randon_forest_regression_model, evaluator, plotter).run()
23 #Run Ridge Regression
24 Controller(dataLoader, preProcessor, ridge_regression_model, evaluator, plotter).run()
25 #Run Support Vector Regression
26 Controller(dataLoader, preProcessor, support_vector_regression_model, evaluator, plotter).run()
27
28
```

21. **9- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

22. **10- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

23. **11- It was easy to extend the behavior of the software with the addition of new models. What is your degree of agreement with the statement? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1- Totally disagree.

2- I disagree.

3- I neither agree nor disagree.

4- I agree.

5- Totally agree.

24. **12- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

25. **13- Adding new models did not imply changing pre-existing code. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

26. **14- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

The plurality of regression models brings the need to run a list of models.

The code below refactors the controller to allow the execution of a list of models and shows an example execution.

Analyze the code:

```
1 class Controller():
2     """Class that orchestrates the execution of a list of models."""
3
4     def __init__(self,dataLoader:DataLoader,preProcessor:PreProcessor,models: list, evaluator: Evaluator, plotter: Plotter):
5         self.__dataLoader = dataLoader
6         self.__preProcessor = preProcessor
7         self.__models = models
8         self.__evaluator = evaluator
9         self.__plotter = plotter
10
11     def __processModel(model,x_train,x_test,y_train,y_test):
12         #Model Training
13         model.fit(x_train,y_train)
14         #Model Predict
15         predictions = model.predict(x_test)
16         #Evaluation
17         self.__evaluator.evaluate(y_test,predictions)
18         #Plot
19         self.__plotter.plot(y_test,predictions)
20
21     def run(self):
22         # Load dataset
23         dataset = self.__dataLoader.dataset()
24         #Preprocessing
25         x_train, x_test, y_train,y_test = self.__preProcessor.preprocess(dataset)
26         #Process Models
27         for model in self.__models:
28             self.__processModel(model,x_train, x_test, y_train,y_test)
29
30
```

```
1 ws = Workspace.from_config()
2 dataset_name = 'revap-u220-pfenc-stream'
3
4 # Create DataLoader
5 dataLoader = DataLoaderFromWorkspace(ws,dataset_name)
6 # Create PreProcessor
7 preProcessor = EspecificPreprocessor()
8 #Create Evaluator
9 evaluator = RegressionEvaluator()
10 #Create Plotter
11 plotter = MatPlotter()
12
13 #Create Models
14 models = [LinearRegressionModel(),RandomForestRegressorModel(),RidgeRegressionModel(),SupportVectorRegressionModel()]
15
16 #Run Models
17 controller = Controller(dataLoader,preProcessor,models,evaluator,plotter)
18 controller.run()
19
20
```

27. **15- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

28. **16- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

29. **17- The models can be replaced without changing the controller. What is your degree of agreement with the statement? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1- Totally disagree.

2- I disagree.

3- I neither agree nor disagree.

4- I agree.

5- Totally agree.

30. **18- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

31. **19- Changes in a model implementation do not imply changes in the controller. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

32. **20- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

Coupling, in software development, refers to the degree to which different components of a system are interconnected and dependent on each other. It is a measure of the dependency between modules or classes within a system. The higher the coupling, the greater the dependency between the components. Low coupling is desirable as it indicates that the parts of the system are independent and can be modified or replaced without affecting the entire system. This leads to more flexible, reusable and maintainable code.

33. **21- The controller has loose coupling with model implementations. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

34. **22- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

Exploratory data analysis shows that we can also solve a classification problem with the same dataset.

We are going to perform software maintenance to allow the use of Linear Support Vector Machines and Support Vector Machines algorithms in classification predictions.

The code below adds new Model implementations, through the LinearSVCModel and SVCModel classes.

Analyze the code:


```
1  from sklearn.svm import SVC
2  from sklearn.svm import LinearSVC
3
4
5  class LinearSVCModel(Model):
6      def __init__(self):
7          self.model = LinearSVC()
8
9
10 class SVCModel(Model):
11     def __init__(self):
12         self.model = SVC()
13
14
```

The inclusion of classification algorithms brings a new need, our evaluation algorithm is currently only able to evaluate regression algorithms.

The code below adds a classification evaluator.

Analyze the code:

```
1 from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, precision_score, recall_score, f1_score
2
3
4 class ClassifierEvaluator(Evaluator):
5     """Class that contains operations necessary to evaluate a classification model."""
6
7     def calculate_accuracy_score(self,y_test,predictions):
8         """Method that returns the accuracy score."""
9         return accuracy_score(y_test,predictions)
10
11     def calculate_precision_score(self,y_test,predictions):
12         """Method that returns the precision score."""
13         return precision_score(y_test,predictions)
14
15     def calculate_recall_score(self,y_test,predictions):
16         """Method that returns the recall score."""
17         return recall_score(y_test,predictions)
18
19     def calculate_f1_score(self,y_test,predictions):
20         """Method that returns the f1 score."""
21         return f1_score(y_test,predictions)
22
23     def evaluate(self,y_test,predictions):
24         print('accuracy:',self.calculate_accuracy_score(y_test,predictions))
25         print('precision:',self.calculate_precision_score(y_test,predictions))
26         print('recall:',self.calculate_recall_score(y_test,predictions))
27         print('f1-score:',self.calculate_f1_score(y_test,predictions))
28
29
```

35. 23- What is your perception about understanding the source code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1 - Very hard.
- 2 - Hard.
- 3 - Normal.
- 4 - Easy.
- 5 - Very easy.

36. **24- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

37. **25- The operations in the evaluator implementations are properly segregated *
for evaluation of classification and regression algorithms. What is your
degree of agreement with the statement?**

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

38. **26- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

Having more than one evaluation algorithm implies selecting the correct evaluation algorithm for each model.

The code below creates a model type to indicate the appropriate evaluator for each model. Refactors the abstract Model class by including the type() and evaluate() methods. The type() method is an abstract method that forces all model implementations to indicate what their type is, and the evaluate() method creates the evaluation operation, but internally delegates its operation to the appropriate evaluator via the model type.

Analyze the code:

```
1  from enum import Enum
2
3
4  class ModelType(Enum):
5      """Enumerator that represents the model types and their respective evaluators."""
6      REGRESSION = RegressionEvaluator()
7      CLASSIFICATION = ClassifierEvaluator()
8
9
10 class Model(ABC):
11     """Abstract class that contains operations of a Model."""
12
13     def fit(self, x_train, y_train):
14         """Method to fit the model."""
15         self.model.fit(x_train, y_train)
16
17     def predict(self, x_test):
18         """Method to do predictions."""
19         return self.model.predict(x_test)
20
21     @abstractmethod
22     def type(self):
23         """Method that returns type of a Model, ModelType."""
24         pass
25
26     def evaluate(self, y_test, predictions):
27         """Method that performs the evaluation of the model."""
28         self.type().value.evaluate(self, y_test, predictions)
```

39. **27- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

40. **28- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

Including the type() abstract method in the model forces all model implementations to be refactored to indicate what their type is.

The code below refactors the models to indicate what type they are.

Analyze the code:

```
1 class LinearRegressionModel(Model):
2     def __init__(self, is_normalized=True):
3         self.model = LinearRegression(normalize=is_normalized)
4
5     def type():
6         return ModelType.REGRESSION
7
8
9 class RandomForestRegressorModel(Model):
10    def __init__(self, number_of_estimators= 100, SEED = 0):
11        self.model = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=number_of_estimators, random_state=SEED)
12
13    def type():
14        return ModelType.REGRESSION
15
16
17 class RidgeRegressionModel(Model):
18    def __init__(self, L2_multiplier=1.0):
19        self.model = Ridge(alpha= L2_multiplier)
20
21    def type():
22        return ModelType.REGRESSION
23
24
25 class SupportVectorRegressionModel(Model):
26    def __init__(self, kernel_type = 'rbf', regularization_parameter = 100):
27        self.model = SVR(kernel=kernel_type, C= regularization_parameter)
28
29    def type():
30        return ModelType.REGRESSION
31
32
33 class LinearSVCModel(Model):
34    def __init__(self):
35        self.model = LinearSVC()
36
37    def type():
38        return ModelType.CLASSIFICATION
39
40
41 class SVCModel(Model):
42    def __init__(self):
43        self.model = SVC()
44
45    def type():
46        return ModelType.CLASSIFICATION
47
48
```

41. **29- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

42. **30- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

The code below refactors the controller to delegate evaluation to the model and shows a running example.

Analyze the code:

```

1 class Controller():
2     """Class that orchestrates the execution of a list of models."""
3
4     def __init__(self,dataLoader:DataLoader,preProcessor:PreProcessor,models: list, plotter: Plotter):
5         self.__dataLoader = dataLoader
6         self.__preProcessor = preProcessor
7         self.__models = models
8         self.__plotter = plotter
9
10    def __processModel(model,x_train, x_test, y_train,y_test):
11        #Model Training
12        model.fit(x_train,y_train)
13        #Model Predict
14        predictions = model.predict(x_test)
15        #Evaluation
16        model.evaluate(y_test,predictions)
17        #Plot
18        self.__plotter.plot(y_test,predictions)
19
20    def run(self):
21        # Load dataset
22        dataset = self.__dataLoader.dataset()
23        #Preprocessing
24        x_train, x_test, y_train,y_test = self.__preProcessor.preprocess(dataset)
25        #Process Models
26        for model in self.__models:
27            self.__processModel(model,x_train, x_test, y_train,y_test)
28
29

```

```

1 ws = Workspace.from_config()
2 dataset_name = 'revap-u220-pfenc-stream'
3
4 # Create DataLoader
5 dataLoader = DataLoaderFromWorkspace(ws,dataset_name)
6 # Create PreProcessor
7 preProcessor = EspecificPreprocessor()
8 #Create Plotter
9 plotter = MatPlotter()
10
11 #Create Models
12 models = [LinearRegressionModel(),RandomForestRegressorModel(),RidgeRegressionModel(),SupportVectorRegressionModel(),LinearSVCModel(),SVCModel()]
13
14 #Run Models
15 controller = Controller(dataLoader,preProcessor,models,plotter)
16 controller.run()
17
18

```

43. **31- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

44. **32- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

Finalization

45. 1) What good practices do you think would help understanding machine learning code? *

46. 2) Do you have any other suggestions to improve understanding of machine learning code?

47. 3) Are you available to answer a few more questions? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes.

No.

Google Formulários

